

ISic1591

I.Sicily inscription 1591

Language

Punic

Type

dedication

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Motya

Place of origin (modern)

Moza

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mozia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645048

Bibliography

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1986. Scavi a Mozia - le iscrizioni. Rome. At no.14

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